

Metadata best practices

Help us to help you – the more of these guidelines you can follow the less time we will spend processing your data. This leaves more time to spend on analysis. If your data are prepared so an outsider can understand, everyone benefits.

Be consistent

- Upper/lowercase are treated as separate entities
- Use the same symbol for missing values e.g. NA, blank

	A	B
1	PatientID	Menopausal_State
2	230001	Pre-Menopausal
3	230002	Pre-Menopausal
4	230003	Post-Menopausal
5	230004	Pre-Menopausal
6	230005	Pre-Menopausal
7	230006	Post-Menopausal

	A	B
1	PatientID	Menopausal_State
2	230001	Pre-Menopausal
3	230002	Premenopausal
4	230003	Post Menopausal
5	230004	Pre-Menopausal
6	230005	Pre-menopausal
7	230006	Post-menopausal

Avoid spaces where possible

- Use underscores (_) instead of spaces in headings
- No empty space before or after words

	A	B
1	Time	Treatment
2		24 Control
3		24 Carbenicillin
4		48 Control
5		48 Carbenicillin
6		72 Control
7		72 Carbenicillin

	A	B
1	Time	Treatment
2		24 Control
3		24 Carbenicillin
4		48 Control
5		48 Carbenicillin
6		72 Control
7		72 Carbenicillin

Use clear file names

- If many files are shared, please name them consistently

Name
plasma_plate_1.csv
plasma_plate_2.csv
plasma_plate_3.csv
plasma_plate_4.csv

Name
batch 3.csv
data for CBF.csv
final batch.csv
second batch data.csv

Include a data dictionary

- Acts as a column key, see example file
- Lists all variables as they are named in your data, with a short explanation for each
- Where relevant include units, range of measurements and expected categories

Use consistent IDs

- Lets us match data and entries across separate files
- If subject ID is contained within a sample ID, let us know in the data dictionary

file_name	patient_ID	group
P0001_A1	P0001	alzheimers
P0002_A2	P0002	alzheimers
P0003_A3	P0003	alzheimers
P0004_C1	P0004	control
P0005_C2	P0005	control
P0006_C3	P0006	control

file_name	patient_ID	group
P0001_A1.csv	P1	alzheimers
P0002_A2.csv	P2	alzheimers
P0003_A3.csv	P3	alzheimers
P0001_C1.csv	P001	control
P0002_C2.csv	P002	control
P0003_C3.csv	P003	control

Be mindful of dates and times

- Write dates as YYYY-MM-DD
- List times in a separate column

Date
2023-07-06
2022-12-14
2023-09-31

Date
06/07/2023
12/14/2022
31/9/2023

Avoid quotes and special characters

	A	B	C	D
1	Batch	Treatment	Percentage_recovered	Sex
2	Batch 1	A		10 M
3	Batch 2	B		30 F
4	Batch 3	AB		50 F

% / # " ' () & * \$

	A	B	C	D
1	Batch	Treatment	Recovered	M/F
2	Batch #1	A	10%	M
3	Batch #2	B	30%	F
4	Batch #3	A&B	50%	F

Include metadata for each experimental sample

- Share batch numbers and dates of measurements with us
- Make any repeated measurements of the same source clear and obvious

Avoid certain Excel features

- Excel converts some gene symbols to dates, so use another identifier if possible e.g. Ensembl or Entrez IDs

	A	B	C
1	GeneID	Expression	Condition
2	ENSG00000099785	8.75	Drug
3	ENSG00000180096	8.44	Drug
4	ENSG00000173077	9.01	Drug
5	ENSG00000099785	6.35	Mock
6	ENSG00000180096	5.61	Mock
7	ENSG00000173077	5.03	Mock

	E	F	G
1	Symbol	Expression	Condition
2	MARCH2	8.75	Drug
3	SEPT1	8.44	Drug
4	DECI	9.01	Drug
5	MARCH2	6.35	Mock
6	SEPT1	5.61	Mock
7	DECI	5.03	Mock

	I	J	K
1	Symbol	Expression	Condition
2	Mar-01	8.75	Drug
3	Sep-01	8.44	Drug
4	Dec-01	9.01	Drug
5	Mar-01	6.35	Mock
6	Sep-01	5.61	Mock
7	Dec-01	5.03	Mock

- Avoid colour coding and merging cells; these often cannot be read by other software

	A	B
1	patient_ID	Grop
2	Patient_1	Alzheimer
3	Patient_2	Alzheimer
4	Patient_3	Alzheimer
5	Patient_4	Control
6	Patient_5	Control
7	Patient_6	Control

patient_ID
Patient_1
Patient_2
Patient_3
Patient_4
Patient_5
Patient_6